
Network information extraction from medieval trial records combining LLM-based coreference resolution with string matching in pre-existing lists of persons

David Zbiral^{*1}, Gideon Kotzé¹, Zoltán Brys¹, Robert L. J. Shaw¹, Tomáš Hampejs¹, and Andres Karjus²

¹Masaryk University [Brno] – Czech Republic

²Tallinn University – Estonia

Abstract

Introduction

The extraction of person-to-person relations from textual corpora using Large Language Models (LLM) has been successfully tested (Anuradha et al. 2023; Baptiste, Armand, and Henriot 2023; Wadhwa, Amir, and Wallace 2023) and is less costly than their manual collection. However, our knowledge of the reliability of some crucial components, especially coreference resolution of persons, is still limited for historical administrative documents, often characterized by orthographic variation, the use of roles instead of names etc. Our objective was thus to test a pipeline extracting network data from medieval trial records under different conditions as to the availability of pre-existing data in order to (1) facilitate decisions on manual data collection to optimise network data extraction, and (2) evaluate the usability of automatically extracted data by comparing network analysis results achieved on them with those achieved on ground-truth data.

Method and data

We processed a register of depositions from Bologna around the year 1300 (ca. 120k tokens, ca. 20k verbal clauses). We combined the use of LLM with custom string regularization and matching against pre-existing lists of persons. We evaluated the pipeline under four conditions, in an ascending order of how extensively pre-existing person data were used: (C1) not using LLM and relying only on connecting deponents with people they named through shared page number in an index of persons (baseline); (C2) matching LLM-extracted name strings only against the full index of names for the whole register; (C3) matching LLM-extracted name strings against pre-existing manually compiled sublists of persons specific to individual documents within the register; and (C4) matching LLM-extracted name and trial role strings against both document-specific sublists of persons and metadata on trial roles (deponent, inquisitor, notary). Our expectation was that C4 will outperform the other conditions.

Under C2-C4, we segmented the documents into verbal clauses, using the end-to-end Latin annotation and dependency parsing pipeline LatinCy (Burns 2023). For each clause, we constructed an LLM input merging the data point variables and instructions. We then processed this data using a commercial LLM, GPT-4o (model version gpt-4o-2024-08-06, zero-shot or

^{*}Speaker

in-context learning approach) via the OpenAI API with a total cost of ca. 40 USD.

The LLM part had two steps: (1) In a first prompt (P1), we instructed the LLM to classify any verbal clause as Valid or Invalid, Real or Unreal (presented as something which actually happened vs. hypothetical statement, question etc.), and as description of Trial vs. content of Testimony. (2) In a second prompt (P2), applied only to clauses evaluated as Valid, Real, AND Testimony through P1, we instructed the LLM to extract a list of human subjects and objects of the clause, returning the string describing them, their type (Person or Group), syntactic role (Subject or Object) and gender.

We then dropped groups, applied replacement operations to persons' name and trial role strings (esp. to lemmatize and regularise them), and matched the regularised strings against preexisting data as defined by the relevant condition. We produced a list of edges, each connecting all person actants of a clause, i.e. persons doing or undergoing something together. Finally, we transformed the extracted data for comparison with a manually constructed incrimination network from the same register (Riccardo et al. 2024).

We evaluated the performance in two ways. Firstly, we expressed the precision and recall of P1, P2 and ID matching using a manually annotated random sample of clauses (N=901). Secondly, we transformed the C2-C4 (C1 already comes in that form) interaction data into an incrimination network analogous to our ground-truth (GT) sublists of persons incriminated by each deponent, and compared C1-C4 incrimination network metrics with GT incrimination network metrics similarly to the evaluation of robustness of network metrics to data loss (Valeriola 2021). We compared node centrality rankings using Kendall's rank correlation coefficient (Kardos, London, and Vinkó 2020). We also applied Exponential Random Graph Models (ERGM, Hunter et al. 2008; Lusher, Koskinen, and Robins 2012) for each network (GT and C1-C4) and compared Beta and p-values of various terms (reciprocity, gender mixing patterns, outdegree variance, etc.).

Results 1: Matching against manual gold-standard data

In P1, we achieved precision 0.88 and recall 0.66; in P2, precision 0.75 and recall 0.80. In local string matching to get from P2 string to a person ID, we achieved, under C4, precision 0.74 and recall 0.45 (F1 score 0.56), preferring non-match to a more tentative match. Recall remains below expectations; precision is fair given the string variation and the number of candidate IDs. C3 and C4 contrast in performance with C2, where the lack of sublists of persons prevented us from achieving ID matching precision higher than 0.34 and recall higher than 0.21.

Results 2: Network comparisons

F1-scores for edges varied across extraction methods, starting at 0.21 for C1 (baseline) and improving to 0.31 under C2. C3 and C4 brought a significant improvement, reaching 0.77 and 0.76, respectively. Kendall's rank correlation coefficient for the baseline method (C1) was 0.55 for degree centrality and 0.49 for betweenness centrality, while C2 showed slightly lower values of 0.47 and 0.45. C3 and C4 achieved higher agreement with GT (0.79–0.82). In the incrimination network, we observed a slight deterioration from C3 to C4.

A similar ERGM model applied to GT and the extracted graphs revealed similar differences. For example, the tendency for edges between females was significant in GT ($B = 1.1$, $p < 0.001$), but absent in C1 ($B = -0.03$, $p = 0.50$). In contrast, C2 ($B = 0.45$, $p = 0.002$), C3 ($B = 1.7$, $p = 0.001$) and C4 ($B = 1.4$, $p = 0.005$) more closely mirrored GT.

Discussion

Under C3-C4, our pipeline provided research results comparable to those achieved on GT. By contrast, under conditions using less pre-existing data, the extracted data seems only usable for studying the broadest patterns. Approaches based on even less pre-existing data

will perform worse. Our results constitute a caveat for network data extraction without the support of pre-existing data.

References

<https://aclanthology.org/2023.ranlp-1.13>
<https://doi.org/10.46298/jdmdh.11756>
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13278-020-00693-0>
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2305.04365>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13935366>
<https://doi.org/10.25517/jhnr.v6i1.105>
<https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2023.acl-long.868>

Keywords: LLM information extraction, network data extraction, coreference resolution, person disambiguation, historical trial records, inquisition